

Influence of time of rice ragged stunt virus infection on deepwater rice yield

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Two deepwater rice varieties susceptible to rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV), KTH123 (early), and PC56 (late), were grown in pots and inoculated with viruliferous brown planthopper (BPH) at five growth stages to test the hypothesis that in deepwater rice most field transmission happens before flooding. There were 3 plants/pot and 3 replications/treatment. A second set of plants treated in the same way was exposed to an equal number of nonviruliferous BPH to eliminate the effect of feeding on yield and plant growth. Plants were sown on 17 May and kept in a normal screenhouse for the first two inoculations. On 16 Jul the pots were transferred to screened metal tanks and the water level was raised to elongate the plants. The last three inoculations

were carried out in the metal tanks. Virus symptoms were recorded during the plant development and grain yield and yield components were measured at maturity.

Grain yield was zero or negligible in both varieties following inoculation in the late seedling stage (60 days after seeding [DS]) and was reduced by about 50% with inoculation in the early seedling and early elongation stages (see figure). RRSV symptoms developed in many plants inoculated at those three growth stages. After mid-elongation stage, inoculation did not significantly lower yields although a few disease symptoms did develop. Yield reduction was caused by absence of panicles or fewer and smaller ones. The disease also reduced plant length. The effect of feeding of 20 hoppers/plant for 24 hours in the late seedling stage is shown in the figure.

Results indicate that major virus transmission takes place early in the season before deep flooding and resistance screening can be done at seedling stage. It may be possible to limit the disease by controlling vector populations before flooding.

Effect of time of inoculation with RRSV on the grain yield of deepwater rice, Bangkok, Thailand, 1982.

Pest management and control INSECTS

Outbreak of rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Walker) in Manipur, India

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A serious outbreak of rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* occurred in the Imphal Valley of Manipur during late Oct 1982 after unusually heavy Feb to Sep rainfall that caused repeated flooding. Oct was comparatively dry. Caterpillar outbreaks were severe in flood-prone areas, particularly in East and Thoubal Blocks of the valley. Many larval-pupal parasites were observed.

Recently introduced varieties Punshi and Phouibi, planted to 50% and 25% of the cultivated area, were seriously damaged. In the East Block 75% of the grain was damaged in some fields. Degree of

Table 1. Incidence of rice ear-cutting Caterpillar on 4 varieties of paddy.^a

Variety	Tillers (no./hill)			Insects (no./hill)		
	Total	Productive	Unproductive	Total	Larvae	Pupae
RCM3 (Moirangphou/Jaya)	19.5 a	13.5 a	7.3 a	10.9 a	6.2 a	5.2 a
Punshi (IR661-1-140-3-2/Phouren)	14.5 b	10.7 b	4.3 b	3.0 b	2.0 b	1.5 b
IR24 (IR8/IR127-2-2)	14.0 b	11.4 b	3.1 c	2.2 b	2.2 b	0.5 b
Moirangphou (local)	11.5 c	11.0 b	1.0 d	0.5 c	0.5 c	0.5 b
SE	1.03	0.80	0.31	0.92	0.51	0.50
CD (<0.05)	2.05	1.64	0.63	1.90	1.00	1.02

^a The figures are $n + 0.5$ transformation of the original values. In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

infestation was recorded based on number of larvae and pupae/hill on 4 rice varieties grown in a 1-ha plot in Khumbong (West - II Block). Caterpillar infestation rose with the number of green, unproductive tillers (Table 1). The caterpillar population was greatest on RCM-3 followed by that in Punshi, IR24,

Moirangphou, Jaya, Mashuri, CH988, CH1039, Phouren, and Kumbi. Many other local varieties grown in small pockets had little or no damage.

Malathion and BHC dust were recommended to control the pest. Spray formulations of insecticides, however, also were used by some farmers. When pesti-